

Facial Paralysis: Karmic Cause and Resolution

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ABSTRACT

Facial paralysis (FP) is a debilitating condition that severely affects physical function, appearance, and emotional well-being. Chronic FP, in particular, remains challenging to treat with conventional medical approaches. While modern medicine has identified causes such as nerve injury, infections, and trauma with available treatments including medications, surgery, and physical therapy, many patients do not achieve full recovery. This suggests the presence of deeper, often overlooked contributing factors. Emerging spiritual case studies point to karmic obstacles, ancestral debts, spiritual disturbances, and moral transgressions as potential underlying causes of FP. In this context, the integration of Dharma-based approaches, such as the Five Golden Buddhist Practices, offers a promising complementary pathway for healing. Through the sincere application of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, patients have reported complete recoveries from acute, subacute, and chronic forms of FP, indicating a strong connection between spiritual causes and the condition. This study proposes a novel perspective on the etiology of FP and introduces an effective, Dharma-grounded treatment approach.

Keywords: Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, Golden Buddhist Practices, Karmic Obstacles, Spirits, Facial Paralysis, Healing

Introduction

Facial paralysis (FP) is a neurological condition, specifically involving the facial nerve. FP causes unilateral paralysis, functional impairments, and asymmetry, reducing overall aesthetics. Secondary complications such as hyperkinesia or synkinesis can result in reduced quality of life, including social isolation and deteriorating mental health [1]. These impairments may also increase the risk of corneal damage and cause profound psychosocial effects due to altered facial appearance and reduced emotional expressivity [2,3].

Current therapeutic approaches include conservative management with physical therapy and pharmacological interventions, such as botulinum toxin for synkinesis, as well as surgical options to restore function and symmetry [3,4]. Despite advances, treatment outcomes vary. This highlights the need for a deeper understanding of the underlying etiology and the development of more effective therapeutic strategies.

According to a recent study, FP can be classified into three stages: acute FP (AFP) (<3 months), subacute FP (SFP) (3–6

months), and chronic FP (CFP) (>6 months). To minimize synkinesis before its onset, earlier medical intervention leads to better outcomes [5].

Our previous study documented a case in which a paralyzed bedridden woman made a full recovery after practicing the Dharma Gems of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door [6]. This case offers a valuable clue for exploring whether this Dharma Door could be applied to the treatment of AFP, SFP, and CFP, potentially helping sufferers escape the sea of suffering.

Mechanisms & Solutions

From a medical perspective, the etiologies of FP are diverse, including idiopathic causes such as Bell's palsy, traumatic injuries, neoplastic processes, infectious agents, neurological disorders, and more [7-11]. Despite these understandings, many AFP patients still progress to CFP, suggesting that current medical theories have yet to uncover the true underlying mechanisms, let alone a definitive cure.

Our previous studies have shown that when medical problems cannot be resolved by doctors or medication, turning to Dharma often leads to unimaginable outcomes. In addition to our previously reported case of a paralyzed patient who regained health through

Buddhist practice [6], we have also documented cases where neurological diseases such as autism spectrum disorder (ASD), myasthenia gravis, Parkinson's disease (PD) Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), and Alzheimer's Diseases (AD) were effectively treated or even cured through Dharma practice [12-16]. To gain a deeper understanding of the mechanisms underlying FP, we present 14 Dharma dialogues in which Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu explains the true causes of these diseases leading to their successful recovery. Among these dialogues, 9 focus on etiology, 3 on recovery, and 2 on prevention.

Etiology

Q&A 1. Mother's CFP Was Due to Ancestral Killing Karma (Excerpt) [17]

(This dialogue took place in a Totem Reading session during the Dharma Conference in Singapore on February 18, 2017)

Master: Please speak.

Twin Girls: Thank you, Master Lu. Thank you, Guan Yin Bodhisattva. We are the twin sisters. Our father, PZ, passed away on March 2, 2016. Could you help us see where he is now?

Master: Did you recite Buddhist scriptures for him? Did your mother recite for him?

Twin Girls: Yes, we did.

Master: PZ... Your father died from a sudden incident. He passed away in great pain, didn't he?

Twin Girls: Yes.

Master: Congratulations, your father is now in the Desire Realm Heaven (欲界天).

Twin Girls: Thank you, Master. Thank you, Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

Master: He said, "To make my children believe, I will tell you something." One of you twins has a large mole on your body—who is it?

Girl on the left: Me.

Master: Let us give her a round of applause. Do you believe in Buddhism now?

Twin Girls: Yes, we do.

Master: That is good. You should start reciting Buddhist scriptures. Do you understand?

Twin Girls: Yes, we do.

Master: Be good children, alright?

Twin Girls: Could you also check our mother's totem? She was born in 1966, Year of the Horse. When she gave birth to us, she had FP that lasted for ten years. It has improved a lot now. How many Little Houses does she need to recite?

Master: Your mother's family has heavy killing karma—your maternal grandfather's side of the family.

Mother of the girls: Yes, yes.

Master: See? If you do not applaud, I can not read it.

(Audience applauds)

Master: Thank you all. I am grateful.

Master: To save people, we must be joyful. Practicing Buddhism should be happy. Cultivating the mind is about breaking through delusions and awakening to wisdom. Practicing Buddhism is not about bitter asceticism. If the more you practice, the more depressed you feel, you must reflect deeply. If you are suffering more from your practice, then you are walking the wrong path. Practicing Buddhism should fill you with Dharma joy.

(Audience applauds)

Twin Girls: How many Little Houses do our mother's karmic creditors need?

Master: 280.

Twin Girls: Thank you!

Master: Help your mother properly, and tell her to go fully vegetarian now.

Twin Girls: She's already a full vegetarian.

Master: What about the two of you?

Twin Girls: Half vegetarian.

Master: What do you mean by half-vegetarian?

Twin Girls: We eat vegetarian on the 1st and 15th of the lunar month.

Master: Let me ask you, don't chicken feet look like a baby's hands?

Twin Girls: Yes.

Master: So you are eating baby hands? Let me tell you—when meat enters your stomach, it sticks to your intestines. Did you know that? Over time, it rots your intestines, understand?

Twin Girls: Yes.

Master: You are so young, and your intestines are already unclean? You know whatever you eat, your body smells like it, right?

Twin Girls: Right.

Master: If you eat smelly foods like onions and garlic, you will smell like them. Right?

Twin Girls: Right.

Master: So if you eat rotten meat, meat that spoils quickly without refrigeration, won't your body start to smell too?

Twin Girls: Yes.

Master: Then why not eat vegetarian? Being vegetarian is so good.

Twin Girls: Understood.

Master: Listen to Grandpa Lu. Make a vow today—both of you go fully vegetarian. Your mother's health will get better and better. Are you willing to eat vegetarian to help your mother recover?

Twin Girls: Yes, we are.

Master: Willing!? Good. I have transformed two more people today.

(Audience applauds)

Q&A 2. Severe FP Due to Lack of Moral Virtue, Has Undergone Punishment in the Underworld [18]

(This dialogue took place in Totem Reading over the phone on April 5, 2018)

Caller: Hello, Master! Please check someone born in 1958, the Year of the Rooster. He has severe FP and has undergone surgery. He has recited over 3,000 Little Houses over the past three years, but he has not recovered. I would like to ask what the reason is.

Master: He was dragged down and has undergone punishment in the underworld. He lacks moral virtue especially *yin de* (阴德) (hidden or invisible virtue).

Caller: Should he recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*?

Master: Yes, five times a day.

Caller: How many Little Houses does he need to recite? And how many lives to release?

Master: He needs to recite 240 more Little Houses and release 3,400 fish.

Caller: Got it. Thank you, Master! Thank you, Bodhisattva!

Q&A 3. FP: Blood Circulation Issues Are Karmic Obstacles-Related Illnesses [19]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on June 24, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! My child recently I noticed that the left side of his face is larger than the right. Could this be due to a spiritual being?

Master: It is not a spirit. It is FP caused by a problem with the blood circulation system! You must be very careful it could worsen and lead to sudden twitching or spasms. This is a karmic obstacles-related illness! You must start reciting Little Houses for him right away.

Caller: How many Little Houses should I recite?

Master: You will need to recite quite a few. Start with 108.

Caller: If I finish the 108 Little Houses but still have not been able to get through to your radio program, should I continue by reciting 1 to 2 per week?

Master: Yes, keep going—continue until the affected area no longer feels abnormal. He will recover. Also, give him some vitamins and let him eat more fruits. This stage is very important. If it is already visible that one side of the face is larger than the other, that will be a serious issue.

Q&A 4. Poor Blood Circulation Causes Facial Distortion; Master Lu Admonishes Phone Caller Not to Drink Alcohol (Excerpt) [20]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on August 14, 2014)

Caller: Hello, Master! Master Lu, I would like you to take a look at the issue I have with the distortion of my mouth and eyes. It has been over a year and still has not healed. Recently, the distortion has started again. What is going on?

Master: Let me take a look—is it around the neck area?

Caller: It is the mouth and face—my mouth and face are crooked.

Master: It is because your blood is not in good condition. Your blood is not circulating properly. Let me tell you—you must not drink alcohol.

Caller: I do not drink alcohol anymore.

Master: You do not drink now, but this is a problem caused by your past drinking. Do you understand?

Master: You must recite Buddhist scriptures diligently.

Q&A 5 Spirit Causes One Side of the Face to Be Larger—Condition Fluctuates Even After Reciting Little Houses [21]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on October 28, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! A fellow Buddhist practitioner's daughter has one side of her face larger than the other. She has already recited over 400 Little Houses for her daughter's karmic creditors, but sometimes the condition improves and sometimes it worsens.

Master: That is because the spirit has not left yet. Facial asymmetry like that is a classic case of a spiritual problem. It is also affecting her blood circulation and basic physiological functions. The spirit has been there for too long that is the reason. If she had ascended it earlier, it would have been much better. Now, it is not just attached to the child anymore. Her mother also needs to recite Little Houses for her own aborted child.

Caller: Okay, thank you.

Q&A 6. FP: A Human Face Turning Ghost-like Due to Punishment from the Underworld [22]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on January 16, 2015)

Caller: Hello, Master!

Master: Hello.

Caller: A fellow practitioner suddenly developed FP a few days ago. Is this due to a karmic eruption or something else?

Master: It is a karmic eruption. I have already told you—after entering 2015, many people will begin to face retribution. Some people think they are cultivating well, but then suddenly misfortune strikes. On the surface, it looks like they are practicing well.

Caller: He is quite old, born in 1940, in his seventies.

Master: Even at seventy, people can still do bad things. Retribution will still come. There is no escaping it.

Caller: What should he do now?

Master: He needs to receive medical treatment while also reciting the *Heart Sutra* and burning Little Houses for his karmic creditors. Otherwise, the spirit will not leave and the FP will not heal. People who develop FP have already been punished by the underworld—they're on the way down. Since he has not gone down yet, they are already making his face look like a ghost.

Caller: Oh... How many Little Houses should he recite in total?

Master: He needs to recite Little Houses for the rest of his life.

Caller: What about life liberation?

Master: He needs to release 3,000 fish.

Caller: He needs to speed up the recitation of Little Houses, right?

Master: Yes. And do the life liberation properly.

Caller: I couldn't get through to the totem reading line a few days ago.

Master: Remember, in situations like this, he must also receive facial massage while reciting the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*. He must keep repenting in his heart otherwise, recovery will be very difficult.

Caller: Oh, how many times should he recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* each day?

Master: Five times a day.

Caller: Anything else to be mindful of?

Master: Nothing else. Just tell him to watch his mouth—stop speaking recklessly. You will see, after entering 2015, the heavenly timing is becoming more urgent, meaning karmic retribution comes much faster. Understand?

Caller: Yes, thank you, Master.

Q&A 7. FP Due to Cheating Others Out of Money in a Past Life [23]

(This dialogue on totem reading took place over the phone on June 2, 2018)

Caller: Hello, Master! A fellow Buddhist practitioner, born in 1954, Year of the Horse, has FP. What aspect should he focus on when reciting the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*?

Master: He has karmic conflicts and heavy karmic obstacles from his past life—very large karmic blocks.

Caller: How many times should he recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*? What should the focus be? How many Little Houses are needed?

Master: He hurt others in a past life—he was a business elite.

Caller: Oh, quite powerful.

Master: He cheated people out of money.

Caller: So should he repent for false speech?

Master: No need. Just repent for the karmic conflicts and karmic obstacles from his past life. Also, recite the *Heart Sutra*.

Caller: How many Little Houses?

Master: 89 Little Houses.

Q&A 8. Feng Shui Issue: Dreaming of a Feng Shui Object Facing the Bed Leading to FP [24]

(Answering Questions from Letters (No. 202) in Master Lu's blog, January 17, 2018)

Question: Last night before going to sleep, I prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva and asked what factors caused my FP. This morning at around 5 a.m., I had a dream. In the dream, directly facing my bed, there was a building by the roadside. On one wall of that building, a Feng Shui object was installed. It was a large rectangular mirror, with a colored phoenix design on each side. The large mirror in the center and the phoenix on the right side were directly facing my bed. The dream was clearly telling me that the Feng Shui object on that building was emitting energy that directly clashed with my bed, and this clash led to my FP. Is it really possible that the Feng Shui setup of that building caused my condition? If so, what should I do?

Answer: Many cases of FP are indeed caused by Feng Shui issues. Poor Feng Shui can lead to FP or even ankle injuries. If one part of the body improves but another part begins to have problems, it often indicates a Feng Shui problem. You should recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* more frequently.

Q&A 9. What Karmic Causes Lead to FP and Cleft Lip [25]
(This dialogue took place over the phone on April 30, 2017)

Caller: Hello, Master! What kind of karmic causes generally lead to FP?

Master: From a medical perspective, FP can result from high blood viscosity, a precursor to stroke, excessive stress, localized brain nerve damage, brain stimulation, or overly rapid nerve twitching. All of these can cause FP.

But from a metaphysical perspective, FP is karmic retribution for making ghostly faces or for telling lies. When a person lies, their facial nerves twitch. If they lie frequently and experience frequent twitching, it can lead to FP.

Caller: Master, is the karmic cause of a cleft lip (harelip) related to fishing in past lives?

Master: Yes, it can be due to fishing, or from lying. People who lie can be born with cleft lips. People who fished in previous lives may also suffer from this retribution.

Recovery

Q&A 10. How to Recite Buddhist Scriptures for FP ? [26]

(Answering Questions from Letters (No. 70) in Master Lu's blog, December 25, 2014)

Question: How should one recite Buddhist scriptures when suffering from FP?

Answer: FP is caused by blockage in the peripheral nervous system. The nerves control the entire facial and bodily organs. When the blood vessels are blocked, the following steps should be taken:

1. Take *Danshen* tablets (Salvia root extract);
2. Undergo facial treatment and physical therapy.
3. Sincerely recite scriptures and pray to the Bodhisattvas, asking for daily blessings and to remove the numbness.

Once the blood circulation is restored, the function of facial nerves will gradually recover.

FP is usually retribution in this lifetime for bad deeds. One should recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* more often.

Q&A 11. Facial Asymmetry, Brain Nerve Damage; Massage as Adjunct Therapy (Excerpt) [27]

(This dialogue took place in Totem Reading over the phone on November 24, 2018)

Caller: Hello, Master! Could you please take a look at a girl born in 2008, Year of the Rat? Her face seems asymmetrical—one side is larger than the other. Her face was already crooked when she was just born.

Master: It is due to nerve damage in the brain, which has also led to FP.

Caller: What should be done now?

Master: She needs to start reciting scriptures immediately. She has two aborted children on her body.

Caller: How many Little Houses are needed?

Master: One child needs 56 sheets, and the other needs 63 sheets.

Caller: Got it. Should she receive massage therapy now?

Master: Yes, massage will help a bit.

Caller: Understood. Master, could you check her lumbar spine? She also has issues there. Is that caused by spirits as well?

Master: Yes. I see a dislocation between the third and fourth vertebrae.

Caller: Can she receive massage therapy for her lumbar spine too?

Master: Yes, she can. Physiotherapy would be good.

Caller: Does she need to recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* for her facial issue?

Master: She should recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* at least 78 times daily, and the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 3 times a day.

Q&A 12. FP: Endocrine and Blood Circulation Issues, Take Danshen Tablets [28]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on July 29, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! My father is very diligent in his Buddhist practice. He recites scriptures daily, keeps up with his daily assignments, recites at least four Little Houses per week, and also makes vows and performs life liberation. However, I have noticed that sometimes his mouth appears a bit crooked. I am not sure what is going on.

Master: Actually, if you look closely, everyone's mouth is a little crooked. But if it is noticeably crooked, that usually points to issues with the endocrine system and blood circulation. It is not caused by reciting scriptures.

Caller: I see. He had this condition even before he started practicing.

Master: Then now, with his Dharma practice, he still has a chance to correct it. He should take some *Danshen* tablets (*Salvia miltiorrhiza*). When blood circulation is poor in certain areas like the mouth, nerves, or facial region it leads to these problems, as they are all controlled by the nervous system.

Caller: Can he pray to Bodhisattva when reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra*?

Master: Absolutely. He can say something like: "May the Bodhisattva bless me with good health, and protect my facial nerves from illness or calamity." That is totally fine.

Prevention

Q&A 13. Severe karmic obstacles in the head—must become vegetarian, or FP may occur [29]

(This dialogue on totem reading took place over the phone on December 29, 2015)

Caller: Hello, Master! Could you please check the physical condition and spiritual presence of a female born in 1986, Year of the Tiger?

Master: The area around her head is in bad shape. She frequently has headaches and dizziness.

Caller: Yes, that is right.

Master: This Tiger is quite troublesome. She has very heavy karmic obstacles. Has she gone fully vegetarian yet?

Caller: Not yet.

Master: “Not yet,” huh... urge her to do so quickly. It is all karmic obstacles ahead. Her whole head is covered in them. If she keeps eating meat, she will suffer from FP in the future.

Caller: Oh, I see.

Master: That means one side of her face will droop. It will look very unpleasant.

Caller: Does she need to offer Little Houses?

Master: Burn 78 Little Houses for her karmic creditors right away. She also needs to perform life liberation and make vows. Her gynecological health is not good either—there is a spirit of an aborted child.

Caller: How many lives should she release?

Master: 1,200 fish. Her karmic burdens are heavy. It is quite troublesome.

Caller: Can she perform the life liberation gradually?

Master: Yes. But she must sincerely repent. She has made many mistakes, especially in relationships. Don't you understand?

Caller: Yes, I understand.

Master: That is good. Let her repent deeply.

Caller: Master, how many times should she recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* each day?

Master: Five times.

Caller: What about her daily recitations the *Great Compassion Mantra*, and *Heart Sutra*?

Master: *Heart Sutra* 17 times, *Great Compassion Mantra* 27 times, *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 5 times, *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 49 times, *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* 49 times.

Caller: Thank you, Master.

Q&A 14. Dream of one side of face bigger than the other—warning of FP [30]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on May 17, 2019.)

Caller: Hello, Master! A practitioner dreamt about another practitioner's child. In the dream, he was helping the child call Master. Master sighed and did not say much, only: “Just recite Buddhist scriptures sincerely.” In the dream, the child had one side of the face larger than the other, unlike in real life. Does this suggest illness, a spiritual cause, or something else?

Master: It indicates illness—FP. One side bigger than the other is a sign of that.

Caller: Even young children can have this?

Master: I will tell you this—if a child is born with underdeveloped brain nerves, or if there are issues with brain cells or the pituitary gland, they can develop all kinds of conditions like strokes or FP. These days, it is not just the elderly—many young people are also suffering strokes.

Caller: Yes, that is true.

Master Lu's teachings reveal that the true causes of FP may stem from a single factor or a combination of karmic, spiritual, physiological, and environmental influences. Beyond the

physical explanations offered by modern medicine such as blood circulation disorders, nerve damage, and endocrine dysfunction many cases of FP are rooted in unresolved karmic debts, ancestral killing karma, a lack of moral virtue, and the karmic consequences of harmful behaviors such as lying or making ghostly faces. Spiritual disturbances, particularly the attachment of spirits such as aborted children or other unsettled beings, can further disrupt blood flow and nerve function, leading to facial asymmetry and paralysis. In some cases, improper Feng Shui arrangements, such as energy clashes caused by mirrors or other objects facing the bed, may also serve as a catalyst for the development of disease.

Recovery from FP, as illuminated by Master Lu, requires comprehensive Dharma practices. Sincere daily recitation of Buddhist scriptures, especially the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, *Great Compassion Mantra*, and *Heart Sutra*, helps to dissolve karmic obstacles and invite blessings from the Bodhisattvas. Reciting and burning Little Houses to repay karmic debts, making vows, performing life liberation (releasing captive animals), and deep repentance are essential components of the healing process. Supplementary practices, such as facial massage, physiotherapy, and the intake of natural remedies like *Danshen* tablets to improve blood circulation, can support and accelerate physical recovery.

Prevention is equally important. Leading a pure and virtuous life, adhering to a vegetarian diet, maintaining moral speech, and accumulating *yin de* (hidden virtues) are key measures to guard against future karmic eruptions. Early spiritual awareness—paying attention to warning dreams and subtle physical signs—can allow one to take proactive steps through Buddhist practice, thereby preventing the manifestation of disease.

Through integrating spiritual cultivation with ethical living, sincere repentance, and physical care, it is possible not only to recover from FP but also to prevent its recurrence, achieving true health of both body and spirit.

The following are three cases in which patients adopted the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door to recover from AFP, SFP, and CFP.

Results

Case 1: My AFP Miraculously Healed in 20 Days Through the Practice of the Five Golden Buddhist Practices

My husband's family are fishermen. Both my father-in-law and my husband had been out at sea catching fish and shrimp. My mother used to gather marine creatures like razor clams, mud snails, small crabs, and clams along the shore. I myself have also caught crabs on the beach. In my daily diet, I consume a lot of live sea animals or freshly caught sea products. These acts incurred heavy karma from killing. Moreover, I had an abortion.

On February 28, 2014, Master Lu gave a Dharma talk at a Dharma Conference in Malaysia, where He enlightened us: “Many children suffer from the karmic consequences of their ancestors—conditions like cerebral palsy, heart problems, autism, and depression are all the result of ancestral killing karma.” My family is a typical case of this: the retribution caused by both ancestral and my own killing karma. My husband and I were often in conflict and quarreled frequently. I did not get

along with my child either. I often felt depressed and confused, and life was very difficult.

In 2019, I was fortunate to encounter the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. Through making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, adopting a vegetarian diet, performing life liberation, and studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, I gradually began to heal from the inside out, and both my mind and body became healthier.

In 2020, my zodiac year, my karmic obstacles erupted, and I developed FP. My mouth and face were crooked, and I could not close one of my eyes. One side of my face felt as if it were being tightly pulled by hundreds of strings—it was stiff and rigid [Figure 1].

Figure 1: I suffered from FP, which caused my mouth to be crooked to one side.

After more than a year of Buddhist practice, I firmly believed that the Bodhisattva would bless and protect me. I did not seek medical treatment or take any medication. I wanted to test whether I could eliminate this karmic obstacle using the Five Golden Buddhist Practices.

I intensified my daily recitation as follows:

1. *Great Compassion Mantra* – 49 times
2. *Heart Sutra* – 39 times
3. *Cundi Dharani* – 49 times
4. *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* – 49 times
5. *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou* – 108 times
6. *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* – 2 times

In addition, for the karma of killing, I vowed to recite:

1. *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* – 5,000 times (49 times daily)
2. *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* – 108 times (2 times daily)

At the same time, I made the following vows:

1. Release 50 fish (I actually released 79 fish and 2 softshell turtles). Every day, I brought a bucket to the market to rescue fish destined for slaughter—sometimes a few, sometimes more than ten.
2. Recite 27 Little Houses. I recited 4–5 Little Houses a day, dedicating one to the aborted child, and the rest to my karmic creditors.

I also prayed to the Bodhisattva to help eliminate my karmic obstacles by using the merits and virtues of helping others awaken spiritually and be liberated.

I continued to recite daily and perform life liberation, and I clearly felt my face stress lightening day by day.

Then came the miraculous moment: in just 20 days, my FP was completely healed, with no aftereffects [Figure 2]! The Bodhisattva truly is the Great King of Medicine.

Figure 2: After making the vows for 20 days, my FP completely disappeared.

Killing karma can also be passed down to future generations. In June 2023, my daughter was diagnosed with mood disorder and depression. She would sleep excessively during the day and could not attend school. At night, however, she became unusually energetic and could not fall asleep. Since childhood, she had a poor appetite, which worsened during her illness. Her stomach constantly gurgled, and she had frequent diarrhea. Sometimes, she would become so sleepy while eating that she had to go back to bed immediately. During this time, her memory was poor, her temper was bad, and she often erupted in anger without cause. She was overly sensitive to sound, accusing her younger brother of walking too loudly and often scolding him harshly. She would suddenly burst into tears, feeling she was the most pitiful and miserable person. She picked at her face until it bled, leaving her features distorted. Her room was always a mess. She became

extremely fearful of seeing people, even close family members, and her mind was completely blank. Nothing could make her happy not even snacks or supermarket trips and she could not walk far.

Through making vows, reciting scriptures, performing life liberation, and deep repentance, i.e., the Four Golden Buddhist Practices, I was able to help my daughter completely recover from depression by the end of 2024. She returned to school and is now studying well.

In this Dharma-Ending Age, I was blessed to encounter such a magnificent Dharma Door. When suffering or in difficulty, I no longer need to rely on others. When I fell ill, I did not become a burden to my family or disrupt my children's schooling. Through practicing the Five Golden Buddhist Practices, and under the blessings of the Bodhisattva, my FP was fully healed. I am deeply grateful from the bottom of my heart.

I hope my story will inspire more predestined sentient beings to believe in Buddhism, begin practicing as soon as possible, and be liberated from suffering to find true happiness.

I will bear the consequences of my own karmic obstacles and will not let fellow practitioners shoulder them.

Fellow practitioner: S117

Case 2: A Miraculous Recovery from SFP Without Medical Treatment

On the day of the Double Ninth Festival in 2019, I had just gotten out of bed when I felt something strange on my face. I asked the friends I usually cycle with, "Do you notice anything unusual about my face?" One of them replied, "Your facial nerves are paralyzed—your mouth is completely crooked to one side." I was shocked. Could it be the same condition as someone I knew who had this issue years ago and still has facial asymmetry when speaking?

The next day, I went to see a doctor and had a CT scan. Fortunately, the results showed it was not a stroke. Some people suggested I try acupuncture. I immediately began going to the Traditional Chinese Medicine hospital for daily acupuncture, but after over a month, there was no improvement. Others recommended a rural hospital offering herbal medicine along with acupuncture. I tried that for many more days, but still saw no clear results.

What made the situation even more frustrating was that I was preparing to go abroad to see family. After much consideration, I still decided to go. Once in a foreign country, I continued to seek treatment, visiting two acupuncture clinics and a massage center, but after several months of effort, there was still no improvement. Treatment costs are very high, and I did not have health insurance. The doctor told me that due to my age, recovery would be slow—essentially implying it would not get better.

After much reflection, I decided to stop all treatments. I thought, "I am getting old anyway; maybe this is my fate. If my mouth is crooked, so be it."

Then, by chance, my daughter picked up a flyer about a free vegetarian event at Guan Yin Hall. It also mentioned a video-sharing session about Master Jun Hong Lu. I was already familiar with Master Lu—I had seen DVDs of His Dharma talks in China. I thought, "Since I am not doing much at home, why not attend?" So, my wife and I went to the event.

That day, the event was packed. We were lucky to get front-row seats. The volunteer hosts spoke words that truly touched our hearts. Since we had watched Master Lu's videos before, we resonated deeply with the messages. After the event, under the guidance of the volunteers, I learned that the cause of my FP was due to a spiritual being occupying my body just as Master Lu had explained in His totem readings. Only by helping this spirit ascend could my body return to normal. I thought, "Since the doctors can not help me, why not give Master Lu's method a try?" So, with the volunteers' guidance, my wife and I started doing daily recitations and offering Little Houses to help the spirit ascend.

The volunteers at the Guan Yin Hall were incredibly patient—they taught us step by step how to make vows, recite scriptures, and perform life liberation. We went to the Guan Yin Hall whenever we had the chance. After some time, without realizing it, our friends began to notice that my mouth was no longer crooked—I had returned to normal!

I was thrilled inside and thought, "This must be the compassionate blessing of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, helping me eliminate illness and pain through recitation, vows, and life liberation. This was the result of daily practice and constantly offering Little Houses to the karmic creditors."

During our time at the Guan Yin Hall, I never once visited the acupuncture clinic. I am truly grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for miraculously healing my FP!

We returned to China earlier than planned. Guan Yin Bodhisattva protected us, and the journey was safe and smooth. After returning home, everyone in the family—children and adults—caught colds and coughs one after another. But my wife and I, both devoted Buddhist practitioners, were not infected at all. Once again, we are deeply grateful for the Bodhisattva's blessings.

Now, we are preparing to set up a Buddhist altar at home. Every day we practice Buddhism and recite scriptures without worry, filled with Dharma joy. Our hearts are full of gratitude and longing for the volunteers at the Guan Yin Hall. Guan Yin Bodhisattva hears all cries and responds to every plea.

Today, I am sharing my story to encourage those who are still hesitating or skeptical: The power of Buddhism is boundless. Only with faith can one enter the door of Dharma. Guan Yin Bodhisattva truly responds to every request. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is real and effective! If you, like me in the past, have run out of options or have tried many methods without healing, I sincerely encourage you to try the Three Golden Buddhist Practices of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. They can solve life's major problems without costing you a penny!

If there is anything improper or not in accordance with the Dharma, I sincerely ask the Bodhisattvas and Dharma Protectors for forgiveness. Once again, I express my heartfelt gratitude to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, to Master Lu, and to all fellow practitioners.

Shared by: A fellow practitioner N118

Case 3: Over a Decade of CFP Cured Completely in Less Than 10 Months Through Practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door!

(Fellow Practitioner's Sharing in Dharma Conference in Jakarta, Indonesia on March 11, 2018)

Greetings to all fellow Buddhist practitioners and friends!

First, I pay my deepest respects to the Namó Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, who rescues all beings from suffering. I also respectfully bow to all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas of the ten directions and three times, as well as all Dharma protectors. I pay homage to my selfless and compassionate Master Jun Hong Lu. I will bear the consequences of my own karmic obstacles.

I come from Shenzhen, China. Today, I would like to share my personal journey of learning and practicing Buddhism. If there is anything improper or not in accordance with Dharma during my sharing, I sincerely ask the compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva for forgiveness.

One day in August 2015, while dining at a restaurant, I ran into my good friend J. We had not seen each other in months, and I noticed she had become more beautiful and her skin looked much better than before. I asked her about it, and she told me it was because she had started reciting Buddhist scriptures. Her explanation piqued my curiosity, and just like that, I was brought to the practice by her and began reciting scriptures myself.

After about ten days of reciting Buddhist scriptures, I started reciting Little Houses. Within less than a month, I dreamed of an image of Guan Yin Bodhisattva floating into my room. After a bit more than two months, I had a dream of a four-legged hairy creature trying to possess my body, and I also saw my deceased father lying beside me. My father used to hunt when he was alive. I was terrified in the dream. At that moment, I suddenly heard Master Lu's voice shout loudly. The creature was scared away, and I woke up from the nightmare. At that point, I had only watched a few hours of Master Lu's totem video disc, and yet His voice could appear in my dream to save me!

After practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door for around six months, I was fortunate to attend Master Lu's Dharma Conference in Jakarta in February 2016 for the first time. I also volunteered at the event and had the honor of shaking Master Lu's hand. After the Dharma Conference, I experienced great changes and became even more diligent with my daily recitations. I was able to recite up to five Little Houses a day and often participated in life liberation events with fellow practitioners.

Then something even more miraculous happened—my FP of more than ten years was completely cured! I had previously

taken Western medicine for over a year with no results, followed by over a year of Traditional Chinese Medicine still no improvement. I had already given up all hope of recovery. Yet, within just ten months of practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I completely regained sensation. This Dharma Door is truly real and extraordinary.

In February 2017, I made a vow at the Singapore Dharma Conference to be a lifelong vegetarian. In April of the same year, I took refuge as a disciple at the Jakarta Dharma Conference.

For over 20 years, I had suffered from frequent nightmares, often waking up terrified in the middle of the night. Now, I no longer have nightmares and sleep soundly through the night. Once I lie down, I fall asleep and stay asleep until morning. Practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door for more than two years has been an incredibly sacred and extraordinary experience.

I have dreamed of Master Lu together with Guan Yin Bodhisattva, dreamed of Master Lu waking me up to witness beautiful golden light shining from Mount Sumeru, and even dreamed of flying with Master Lu... On average, I dream of Master Lu's Dharmakaya about once a month.

Through making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation, I went from being physically weak and sickly to now feeling light and energetic like a swallow. I do not need to go to the hospital. Even reciting 8 to 10 Little Houses a day doesn't make me feel tired.

I am truly grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva and to Master Jun Hong Lu. Thank you all!

Shared by: Z119

Discussion

FP poses complex physical and psychological challenges, often leading to low self-esteem, anxiety, depression, and sometimes even suicide [31]. Peripheral FP, in particular, is recognized as a disabling condition with significant psychological and social consequences [32]. While traditional medical approaches identify various causes, such as idiopathic origins, trauma, infections, and neoplasms, they frequently fall short of providing definitive explanations or lasting solutions. Even with early treatment, many patients transition from acute to chronic stages, suffering ongoing functional and psychosocial impairments. These limitations highlight the need for alternative perspectives to achieve a more holistic understanding of FP.

The findings presented here suggest that karmic factors, particularly karmic burdens, ancestral killing karma, and the influence of spirits, play a critical role in the onset and persistence of FP. Master Lu's Dharma teachings consistently reveal that FP may result from accumulated karmic debts, including past life actions such as lying, cheating, harming sentient beings, or disrespecting the moral order. Poor Feng Shui arrangements and the presence of attached spirits can further exacerbate physiological dysfunction, leading to facial asymmetry or paralysis (Q&A 1-14).

The recovery cases from AFP to SFP to CFP demonstrate that profound healing is possible through sincere Dharma practice, without reliance on conventional medical treatments (Cases 1-3). Practicing the Golden Buddhist Practices, such as making vows daily scripture recitation, life liberation, repentance, and studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, has enabled patients to dissolve karmic obstacles, heal from FP, and improve their overall physical and psychological well-being. Specifically, daily recitations of the *Great Compassion Mantra*, *Heart Sutra*, *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, and *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*, along with repaying the karmic creditors with Little Houses, proved to be particularly effective.

The application of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door in treating FP echoes our previously reported case of a bedridden, paralyzed patient who fully recovered through Buddhist practice [6], once again affirming the truth and effectiveness of this Dharma Door. In fact, Buddhism not only offers hope for reversing or even curing neurological conditions deemed untreatable by modern medicine [12-16] but it has also shown efficacy in addressing mental illnesses like borderline personality disorder, severe depression, oppositional behavior, and parapsychoarchia (schizophrenia) [33-36]. These therapeutic outcomes go beyond what current medicine can achieve.

In our discussion on chronic constipation, we explained that the medical term “idiopathic” often implies a “spiritual” or “karmic” origin [37]. The same principle applies to FP: when the cause is labeled as “idiopathic”, it indicates an unknown medical origin, which in many cases points to a spiritual or karmic cause: “spiritual FP” or “karmic FP”. This understanding is exemplified by the three cases presented in this article.

A valuable advantage of practicing Buddhism is the early awareness it provides before karmic obstacles fully manifest, allowing for timely spiritual intervention. Warning signs, such as symbolic dreams, subtle physical asymmetries, or emotional disturbances, serve as signals, offering a crucial window for repentance and proactive Dharma practice that may prevent the onset or progression of FP. Even when karmic obstacles have already materialized as physical illness, consistent and intensified spiritual practice can still bring about significant recovery, such as the chronic case lasting more than a decade (Case 3).

Moreover, the success of the patients in overcoming FP through spiritual means offers insight into broader applications: that karmic-related illnesses, once considered incurable, might be approached through karmic resolution and spiritual ascension. This points to a need for further exploration into the integration of spiritual healing with medical science to develop comprehensive treatment frameworks for such complex conditions.

Nonetheless, it must be emphasized that the experiences shared are subject to individual karmic conditions, and outcomes may vary. The spiritual resolution path requires unwavering faith, deep repentance, consistent effort, and the compassionate blessings of the Bodhisattvas.

In summary, Master Lu’s teachings presented in the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door offer an extraordinary complementary approach to understanding, preventing, and healing FP. These

insights may inspire more patients to embrace self-cultivation, ethical living, and Dharma practice as a path not only to physical recovery but also to liberation from deeper karmic suffering.

Conclusion

FP remains a challenging condition with complex etiologies and often incomplete recovery through conventional medical approaches. The cases and dialogues presented in this study reveal that many instances of FP are deeply rooted in karmic burdens, ancestral debts, spiritual disturbances, and violations of moral virtue. These spiritual causes, largely overlooked by modern medicine, offer critical insight into both the origin and resolution of the disease.

Through the sincere practice of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, including daily recitation of Buddhist scriptures, making vows, life liberation, repentance, and studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, patients have achieved remarkable recoveries, even in cases of CFP persisting for more than a decade. These outcomes underscore the transformative power of Dharma practices in dissolving karmic obstacles, restoring physical health, and achieving inner peace.

The integration of spiritual understanding with medical knowledge holds great potential for creating more holistic treatment strategies for karmic-related diseases. Moving forward, further research into the interplay between karmic causality and physical health may open new pathways for healing that transcend the limitations of conventional therapies.

Ultimately, true recovery lies not only in treating physical symptoms but also in cultivating a virtuous heart, repenting for past misdeeds, and harmonizing with the laws of karma. By doing so, individuals can not only overcome suffering in this lifetime but also lay a solid foundation for lasting health and liberation in future lives.

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Ethical Statement

The author did not involve any part of the experimental design, experimental treatments, and result analysis of the patient. All the experimental procedures and practices by the presenters were done by themselves independently.

Statement by Translator and Writer

The 3 stories and 14 Q&A dialogues in the text were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings,

I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

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The contents of the presentation, comments, and discussion, including text, images, and other information obtained from Dharma practitioners, are provided strictly for reference purposes. Due to the unique nature of individual karma, results similar to those experienced by the practitioner may not be replicated. The experiences and advice shared should not be construed as medical advice or a diagnosis.

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